

Pulling the wool over your eyes: Sheep study is the latest victim of corruption and censorship of vaccine safety science

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Mar 2019
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Censorship

Vaccine safety science is settled. By censorship.

This book, *Controversies in Vaccine Safety: A Critical Review*, was released for pre-order by Elsevier, the publisher, in Oct 2017. A month later the book mysteriously disappeared from radar screens. The book had contributions from over 30 authors including Prof. Lluís Lujan and myself, raising numerous vaccine safety questions.

<https://www.booktopia.com.au/controversies-in-vaccine-safety-christopher-a-shaw/prod9780128032541.html>

Recently, Prof. Lujan's group published a paper in *Pharmacological Research*, an Elsevier journal, titled:
Cognition and behavior in sheep repetitively inoculated with aluminum adjuvant-containing vaccines or aluminum adjuvant only.(1).

The editor of the journal, E. Clementi, received a letter from an anonymous source raising concerns about the statistics in the paper. The editor writes to Prof. Lujan outlining the concerns, requesting data for the journal's statistics expert to perform their own review and suggests that the paper be withdrawn!

Prof. Lujan provides detailed responses (2) and data showing that the concerns raised were without merit. The journal's statistics expert reviews the data and agrees with Prof. Lujan. Inexplicably, the editor decides to withdraw the paper!

So it's true, vaccine safety science is settled. But you have to ask how it was settled. The answer is, via censorship of any evidence of vaccine safety problems. As Richard Horton, editor of the *Lancet* wrote, science has taken a turn towards darkness (3). Corruption, censorship, incompetence and fraud dominate medical science (4–10). This is vaccine safety science – settled.

Plotkin pulls the wool over parents' eyes

Vaccine "expert" Dr. Stanley Plotkin was deposed in Jan 2018 (11). The IOM concluded in its 2012 report that (12):

"Conclusion 10.6: The evidence is inadequate to accept or reject a causal relationship between diphtheria toxoid, tetanus toxoid, or acellular pertussis-containing vaccine and autism."

On pg. 255 of the deposition, Attorney Siri asks, referring to the IOM conclusion above: And so for that reason, you're okay with telling the parent that DTaP/Tdap does not cause autism even though the science isn't there yet to support that claim?

Plotkin responds: Absolutely.

And it is not as if Plotkin is the lone bad apple.

Here is Dr. Offit lying about the same thing.

The Notice of proposed rulemaking (NPRM) (13), only specifically states:

"1. The scientific evidence favors a rejection of a causal relationship between MMR vaccine and autism.", based on the IOM 2012 (12) report.

Commenting on the above NPRM, Dr. Offit wrote (14):

"Given the controversy on the issue, however, it would be helpful to explicitly refer to autism in this context – as noted in the NPRM, the evidence supports rejection of a connection between vaccines and autism."

Dr. Offit took NPRM's MMR vs. autism conclusion, lied and generalized it to cover all vaccines and autism.

Conclusion

It should therefore come as no surprise that vaccines have numerous safety problems and sicken millions (15). And the Dr. Plotkins and Offits of the world continue to lie and sicken millions more.

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